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ELECTRIC OPERATED PAPER PLATES MAKING MACHINE

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ABSTRACT

Electric operated Paper plate making machine in which the plates of paper can be easily makes in a very cheap in the cost. Once the machine is made with only it required to the change the shape of the punches and we can get different shapes of plates and paper balls. There are many numbers of hydraulic machines available for making the paper plate and paper balls. It is always demand in the market that machine must be reliable, with small dimension, low construction and maintains cost. Electric operated paper plate making machine is easy to operate by unskilled person. The rate of production plates is almost 30 within 1 minute. Paper plate making machine consist of Motor, Gear box, Chain, Die, Connecting rod, etc. The rotary motion of motor is converted into linear motion by using different mechanism. In this machine we use gear box for speed reduction.

KEYWORDS: Motor, Gear box, Chain, Die, Punches, Connecting rod etc.